

PERCEPTION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL TOOLS IN ONLINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study was to assess Grade 10 students' perceptions of the effectiveness of digital tools in online learning. Utilizing a descriptive-survey research design with random sampling, the study found that students generally have a positive view of digital tools, agreeing that these tools are user-friendly, easy to navigate, and enhance their overall learning experience, engagement, and confidence in knowledge acquisition. Digital tools were seen as beneficial for improving comprehension, engagement, focus, and competence. Most students agreed on the advantages of digital tools, such as increased participation, collaboration, motivation, and productivity. However, there were suggestions for personalized adjustments to better fit individual learning styles. The findings highlight that digital tools contribute to better academic performance and engagement. Consequently, it is recommended that teachers continue traditional content discussions while incorporating digital tools in select topics to boost engagement, understanding, motivation, and performance.

Keywords: Digital Tools, Effectiveness, Online Learning, Perception, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, integrating technology into education is crucial for both learners and educators to access information efficiently. Barrot et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of understanding students' online learning experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting challenges and coping strategies. Chauhan (2018) underscores the need to educate students on navigating digital spaces and tools to foster a healthy relationship with their environment.

The pandemic significantly disrupted education systems globally, transitioning many to online or hybrid modes. Bergdahl (2019) notes that Asian teachers find it particularly challenging to engage students due to the plethora of tools and methods available, often leaving schools confused about the best solutions. The relationship between student engagement in Technology-enhanced Learning (TEL) and digital skills remains underexplored. Antonio et al. (2022) discuss how engaged students learn more effectively, retain information longer, and enjoy learning activities more, advocating for gamification as a strategy to enhance motivation and involvement.

Nadeem et al. (2020) found that gamified elements in digital tools can boost student motivation, improve classroom dynamics, and provide quick feedback, as seen in the increased use of GSRS in higher education. Barrot et al. (2021) further highlight the pandemic's impact on education effectiveness and student well-being, emphasizing the need for adequate preparation and infrastructure for digital learning.

Climans (n.d.) describes digital tools as any technology supporting curriculum creation, including social media, online games, multimedia, and mobile apps. These tools offer immersive experiences through text, images, audio, and video. Aldana (2020) demonstrated that using Kahoot! in high school geometry classes led to higher quiz averages and increased student engagement. Similarly, Navarro et al. (2021) found that students preferred Quizizz for its functionality, ease of use, and enjoyment.

Abaya et al. (2022) indicate a strong link between student engagement and performance, suggesting that gamified learning management systems can enhance academic outcomes. The positive correlation between motivation and involvement supports this finding, with progress bars being particularly effective.

These studies collectively highlight the diverse impacts of digital tools on student engagement and performance, emphasizing the importance of personalized adjustments and adequate preparation for successful online learning integration

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Widayanti (2021), some teachers struggle with using technology for online learning, making it difficult to monitor student activities and responses. The COVID-19 outbreak posed many challenges, but Ivaniuk et al. (2020) found that 73% of teachers actively addressed these issues, highlighting the effectiveness of professional development through webinars, online courses, and workshops. Despite difficulties, teachers have improved their use of online tools for group learning.

Ivaniuk's study aimed to assess distance learning and identify effective online tools. Internal factors such as motivation and study habits, and external factors like the learning environment and resources, impact online education, indicating a need for improvement in both areas.

Cheong et al. (2013) explored gamification in learning, finding that it enhances engagement and learning effectiveness. Their study with 76 undergraduate students using a gamified quiz tool showed positive results, with improvements in learning productivity and performance. However, they recommended that gamification should not be used for assessment and participation should be voluntary.

Munawir et al. (2021) found that gamification increases student enthusiasm and motivation. While effective in engaging students, challenges like limited class hours and learning difficulties persist. The study showed that students enjoyed using Quizizz for learning but faced emotional and behavioral issues.

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of digital tools in online learning for Grade 10 students at the University of Baguio Science High School. Wirani et al. (2022) evaluated Kahoot!, finding that its continued use is influenced by perceived usefulness and individual impact. Satisfaction and gamification elements like competitiveness also play a role. Their findings suggest that integrating gamification into learning can be beneficial during the COVID-19 pandemic, although their study was limited to a specific geographic location. They recommend exploring other platforms like Mentimeter and Quizizz for future research.

Conceptual/Theoretical Framework

Digital educational tools encompass a wide range of resources, including development tools, websites, and learning platforms, that connect students, teachers, and parents to facilitate learning. These tools enhance access to information and comprehension, with a constantly expanding selection.

E-learning platforms provide superior access to resources, faster communication, and better collaboration than traditional methods. They have revolutionized higher education, supporting sustainable education. Alqahtani et al. (2022) found that e-learning is crucial for sustainable development but noted some students struggled with specific competencies, indicating a need for more research on optimal educational paradigms.

Effective technology integration in education is driven by sound teaching practices. Advanced technologies should focus on educational objectives, active engagement, and connecting students to real-world experts. Teachers must clarify the purpose of technology use and promote collaboration, as learning is inherently social. Picciano (2017) suggests that online learning is a distinct form of education, evolving towards an integrated model that combines face-to-face and e-learning.

Gamified elements can enhance motivation, classroom dynamics, and provide rapid feedback, as noted by Nadeem et al. (2020). However, Barrot et al. (2020) found that home educational environments posed significant challenges for students, more so than computer literacy or professional competence. Blegica et al. (2020) concurred, highlighting distractions and barriers in virtual classrooms.

Digital tools, defined by Climans (n.d.) as apps, software, and platforms for communication, collaboration, and engagement, create immersive learning experiences. Aldana (2020) found that Kahoot! review games increased engagement and quiz scores in a high school geometry class. Similarly, Navarro et al. (2021) found Quizizz to be the most effective assessment tool among several studied.

Social networking, gaming, and multimedia can enhance learning. Kahoot! review sessions improved academic performance and motivation (Aldana, 2020). Abaya et al. (2022) noted that gamified learning management

systems can boost student performance, with participation positively correlating with improved attitudes and motivation towards learning.

Significance of the Study

The adoption of digital tools for learning is critical for the education of students at the University of Baguio Science High School, which capitalizes on a web-based curriculum. The objective of the researchers in this study was to determine how effective these digital learning tools are in educating students and what modifications teachers and students must make to get the most out of these digital learning platforms.

Furthermore, the researchers foresaw that their findings would be used to further improve the University of Baguio Science High School's educational technique. The findings of this study helped teachers approach online teaching and contribute to the growth of online activities. Though the results were mostly dependent on the students, the findings of this study were useful to teachers as they will serve as a guideline for what changes they and the school as a whole must make in order to teach students more efficiently and effectively. Additionally, this research also intended to offer students an opportunity to voice their opinions on what adjustments should be made so that everyone can learn effectively and in a timely manner. The researchers' study was heavily focused on the students' perceptions of their engagement with and use of digital learning tools, and the conclusions the researchers drew were based on their perspectives and involvement in this research. Furthermore, this research was used as a reference for future researchers at the University of Baguio Science High School, as well as future studies based on digital learning tools.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study was to determine the perception on the effectiveness of digital tools in online learning of University of Baguio Science High School Students.

The study aimed to specifically address the following:

1. To examine students' use and perceptions of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools for learning.
2. To determine the effectiveness of using Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools for learning.
3. To determine the impact of digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz and how it affects the students in their online learning

III. METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study made use of Descriptive-Survey Research Design. A descriptive study describes the current status of a phenomenon being studied taking into consideration existing conditions in the research environment. It is a survey study because it involves a large number of respondents. Survey research gathers information from a large number of people through the use of a survey questionnaire.

Population and Locale of the Study

The locale of the study is the University of Baguio Science High School. The respondents were students during the current school year, 2023-2024 who were willing to participate in the study. As for the number of people who did participate, the researchers' target was to gain 45 respondents after calculating their margin of error as 10% and confidence level as 90%. The researchers opted to conduct the study during the school year 2023-2024 given that more students have had greater experience with digital learning tools notably Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz. This study focused mainly on the junior high school division, especially those who are in grade 10 from the sections Atomic Physicists, Biophysicists, Molecular Physicists, and Quantum Physicists. The researchers focused on the grade 10 students considering that they have been using digital learning tools since the first year of high school. Additionally, the researchers used Random Sampling.

Data-Gathering Tools

The data-gathering tool for this study is a survey-questionnaire. The questionnaire on Identifying the effectiveness of using digital tools and the student's use and perceptions of digital learning tools is a self-assessment tool formulated by the researcher. The survey-questionnaire comprises four parts. The first part displays the consent form. The second part is to determine the perception of students on digital learning tools. The third part is to determine the effectiveness of digital learning tools. The fourth part is to determine the impact of digital learning tools on students.

Validity of the questionnaire was determined by presenting it to the researcher’s adviser who then approved the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered among the grade 10 students of the University of Baguio Science High School.

Data-Gathering Procedures

Before the gathering of data, the questionnaire was subjected to a validity test. Having been given the go-signal to start gathering data, the researchers asked permission to conduct the study from the Research teacher of the University of Baguio Science High School.

The researchers administered the questionnaire among the grade 10 students of the University of Baguio Science High School, online. Only those who were willing to participate were included in the population of the study. The accomplished questionnaires were **retrieved**/collected by the researcher and were brought for data processing through a statistician.

The processed data was tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Treatment of the Data

Descriptive Statistics was used to describe and summarize the data that were collected or gathered in the study. Specifically, the perceived level of the students was described, analyzed, and summarized using the weighted mean.

Table 1: Scale of Interpretation

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly valued, Always Observed
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	Valued, Often observed
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Less valued, Sometimes observed
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not valued, Not observed

Ethical Consideration

The following ethical considerations were taken into account throughout the conduct of this study: The participant's engagement was voluntary. An informed consent form was provided to the participants before the questionnaire was distributed, thus they were not coerced into participating in the research. Regarding the participants' voluntary engagement, it was stated on the consent form that their participation serves solely academic objectives and that they will receive no cash recompense for their participation. The study ensured that there will be no potential harm, such as psychological or physical harm, would befall the participants. The researchers discussed their ideas and opinions on their methodology and results in an honest and polite manner. If an issue arose between the participants and the researchers, the researchers were held liable for their actions. Once any issues or concerns arose throughout the research or study process, the researchers were quick to approach and ensured that the issue was resolved or addressed promptly and effectively.

The participant's individual identities were not revealed. Additionally, the interview's results were only accessible to the researchers. According to Wall (2017), The Data Privacy Act of 2012 sections include rules that specify how the interview will use the information acquired and how it will completely inform its community (Republic Act. No. 10173, Ch. 1, Sec. 2). This Act will be applied to the interview questions used to collect data. This includes the informed consent of the school, and the participants — University of Baguio Science High School Students. The questionnaire results were used to gather data on the participant's perception of the effectiveness of online digital learning tools. Lastly, the attendees were given the chance to evaluate the findings and make comments before sharing them with others.

As a result, this sensitive data was only utilized for the aforementioned research projects and will be presented in a gathering that the University of Baguio Science High School will provide or at any other potential locations picked by the University of Baguio and given its approval.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: The use and perception of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools for online learning.

Statement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I think digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz are user-friendly.	3.51	SA
2. I think navigating through digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz is easy for me.	3.40	SA
3. I think digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz enhance my overall learning experience.	3.33	SA
4. I think the interactive features of digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz contribute to my engagement with the material.	3.53	SA
5. I think digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz help me gain confidence in my knowledge of our lessons.	3.18	A
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.39	SA

Table 2 shows the level of agreement on the perception of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools in online learning of University of Baguio Science High School students. It can be seen that students strongly agree on the perceptions of using digital tools with a computed mean of 3.39. Based on the collected data and the objectives of the study, the results indicate a generally positive perception among University of Baguio Science High School students regarding the effectiveness of digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz in online learning. The majority of respondents expressed agreement with statements related to user-friendliness, ease of navigation, enhancement of overall learning experience, contribution to engagement with the material, and confidence-building in knowledge acquisition.

The use and perception of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz on online learning

Based on the collected data, the question "I think the interactive features of digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz contribute to my engagement with the material." got the highest point with the weighted mean of 3.53 with a descriptive equivalent of "strongly agree" means that students find the interactivity of these tools highly engaging. Digital tools with interactive elements have the potential to increase user engagement with the information by providing an enjoyable and interesting learning experience. On the other hand, the question that states "I think digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz help me gain confidence in my knowledge of our lessons," has the lowest weighted mean of 3.18 with a descriptive equivalent of only "agree" means that even though these resources might be interesting and improve the learning process, participants' confidence in their understanding of the material may not always increase as a result of them. A person's level of confidence in their knowledge can be affected by a number of factors, such as the difficulty of the topic at hand, their preferred method of learning, and how well these digital tools provide feedback. The participants' general attitude regarding the use of digital tools in their learning is reflected in the overall weighted average score of 3.39. Although most participants thought these tools were helpful, there are some areas, including increasing knowledge and confidence, where they might be improved, according to the overall score.

These findings align with previous literature, such as the study by Cheong et al., (2013), which highlighted the potential of gamified learning activities also known as the gamification theory, like those facilitated by Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz, to enhance student engagement, enjoyment, and learning effectiveness. Additionally, the study by Wirani et al., (2022) emphasized the importance of perceived usefulness, individual impact, and satisfaction in influencing the continued use of digital tools like Kahoot. However, it is notable that a few respondents disagreed or remained neutral on certain aspects, such as the enhancement of confidence in knowledge acquisition. This suggests that there may be room for adjusting or personalizing these digital tools to better fit each student's learning style and needs. In conclusion, the results of this research provide valuable insights into the perception of University of Baguio Science High School students regarding the effectiveness of digital tools in online learning.

Table 3: The effectiveness of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz for online learning.

Statement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I am able to understand my lessons with better clarity through the use of digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	3.09	A
2. I am able to engage in my classes more easily through digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	3.24	A
3. I am able to gain higher grades/scores because of digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	2.80	A
4. I am more focused in my classes when using digital tools for learning such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	2.96	A
5. I am competent in doing my assignments because of digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	2.91	A
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.00	A

Table 3 shows the level of agreement on the effectiveness of using Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools in online learning of University of Baguio Science High School students. It can be seen that students agree on the effectiveness of using the digital tools with a computed mean of 3.00. This means that the effectiveness of the digital tools is often observed by the students.

The effectiveness of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz on online learning

With a mean of 3.24, the question “I am able to engage in my classes more easily through digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.” received the highest point. This indicates that these tools are successful in enriching the learning experience and fostering active involvement among students. Active participation in classes tends to lead to improved attention, participation, and information retention among students. This observation aligns with the findings of Nadeem et al. (2020), who noted that gamified elements can boost student motivation and enhance classroom dynamics. Moreover, a study by Munawir et al. (2021) revealed that implementing gamification strategies led to increased enthusiasm among students, along with a stronger desire to excel academically.

Conversely, the question that states “I am able to gain higher grades/scores because of digital learning tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.80. This suggests that students do not perceive a significant impact on their grades or scores from using these tools. While these tools can enhance the learning process and facilitate comprehension, they may not always translate directly into improved academic performance. This finding may resonate with the insights of Barrot et al. (2020), who highlighted that students' primary challenges were related to their home educational environment, rather than computer literacy or professional competence.

The participants' general attitude regarding the effectiveness of digital tools in their learning is reflected in the overall weighted average score of 3.00. This indicates that students typically find these tools useful for improving their comprehension, participating in class more easily, maintaining focus, and being capable of finishing tasks. However, even if the data appear promising, more observational research is recommended. Taking into account the collected data and findings, some students have different opinions about how effective Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz are for University of Baguio Science High School students' online learning. The aforementioned data is consistent with studies by Barrot et al., (2020), and Blegica et al. (2020), which found that students in virtual classrooms observed technological challenges, psychological and personal barriers, and

both physical and electronic distractions. Therefore, this implies that, depending on their experiences and interests, the effectiveness of using technology and digital tools for learning may vary.

Table 4: The impact of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz on the online learning.

Statement	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I can participate in class much better because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	3.24	A
2. I can collaborate with my classmates and subject teachers more because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	3.22	A
3. I can join my classes with greater motivation because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	2.96	A
4. I can consistently be productive in my classes because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	3.04	A
5. I can learn my materials at my own pace because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz.	2.96	A
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.08	A

Table 4 shows the level of agreement on the impact of using Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools in online learning of University of Baguio Science High School students. It can be seen that students agree on the impact of using digital tools with a computed mean of 3.08. This means that using Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz as digital tools is often observed in the learning of UB Science High School students. As seen in the table above, the weighted mean for every query implies favorable, with most displaying high ranges based on the scale of interpretations. The majority of respondents agree that digital tools have a substantial and beneficial impact on these students' academic success. Parallel to the findings of Antonio et al., (2022) and Cheong et al., (2013), it states that through the integration of game-like elements such as challenges, rewards, and progress tracking into educational activities, students are more engaged and enthusiastic about their learning, leading to increased involvement in class activities, higher levels of effort, and ultimately improved academic outcomes. Nevertheless, it is important to take into account responses that express opposing opinions regarding the impact of digital tools on their learning. According to the standpoints obtained in the study of Evolution, (n.d.), while the e-learning model is an outstanding innovative approach to learning, students encounter additional challenges with this type of schooling, such as emotional and behavioral issues along with educational difficulties. In this case, as shown in the table, students at the University of Baguio Science High School are having trouble grasping their material, leading them to lose motivation and desire to learn.

The impact of Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz on online learning

With a mean of 3.24 and a descriptive equivalent of "Agree," question 1's statement, "I can participate in class much better because of online learning digital tools like Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz," received the highest point. This indicates that the majority of students find that with the help of the said digital tools, students are able to communicate with their teachers better. This correlates with the research of Climans, D. (n.d.), who defines digital tools as any apps, software, and platforms that support communication, collaboration, engagement, and curriculum creation for learners. Digital tools provide a way to implement text, images, audio, and video for an immersive experience that students and teachers can use for better communication.

Question 5: "I can learn my materials at my own pace because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz." along with question 3: "I can join my classes with greater motivation because of online learning digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizizz." received the lowest point with a mean of 2.96 and a descriptive equivalent of "Agree." This suggests that neither improving lesson comprehension nor encouraging

students to attend online classes are aided by digital tools. The data above is consistent with studies by Barrot et al. (2020), which found that students' biggest obstacles were related to their learning environments at home; computer literacy and professional competence posed the least amount of difficulties; and Blegica et al. (2020), which found that students in virtual classrooms observed technological challenges, psychological and personal barriers, and both physical and electronic distractions. Therefore, this implies that, depending on their experiences and interests, the effectiveness of using technology and digital tools for learning may vary.

This section's overall weighted mean was 3.08, which is the descriptive equivalent of "Agree." This indicates that the majority of students thought Quizziz, Padlet, and Kahoot had a significant influence on their online education. However, the analysis of the mean of question 1 (3.24) compared to the means of questions 3 and 5 (2.96) shows that while digital tools are beneficial for boosting student involvement, they are not beneficial for improving comprehension or motivation. This is in line with the findings of Antonio et al., (2022), which states that through Gamification, it boosts student engagement in learning resulting in higher involvement in educational activities. But it is also stated that the students also faced problems in this style of learning like emotional and behavioral problems and learning difficulties. Such as limited class hours in practicing language skills, limited authentic material resources, and too many students in a class. It results in many students losing their motivation and desire to learn (Evolution, n.d).

V. CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

The research findings from the University of Baguio Science High School Grade 10 students' responses indicate a generally positive perception and effectiveness of digital tools such as Kahoot, Padlet, and Quizziz in online learning. With a mean of 3.39, the majority of students strongly agree on the perceptions of using these digital tools, expressing agreement with statements related to user-friendliness, ease of navigation, enhancement of overall learning experience, engagement with the material, and confidence-building in knowledge acquisition. These findings align with previous literature findings emphasizing the potential of gamified learning activities to enhance student engagement, enjoyment, and learning effectiveness.

The majority of students, with a mean score of 3.00, concur that digital tools are useful in raising students' comprehension, engagement, focus, and competence in their studies. With a mean score of 3.08, this indicates that most students are in agreement with the benefits of utilizing digital tools, which include increased participation, collaboration, motivation, and productivity.

However, few students disagreed on certain aspects, suggesting the need for personalized adjustments to better fit individual learning styles and needs. This highlights the importance of ongoing exploration and support for these tools to improve student engagement, learning experiences, and outcomes in online classrooms. The research findings also show that students generally agree on the effectiveness and impact of using digital tools in online learning. Students may have differing opinions and face challenges related to their learning environments, technological issues, and emotional and behavioral concerns.

The effectiveness of these digital learning tools relies on the engagement of students which was consistent with the findings which state that every new application appears to be a possible answer. Learners who can participate in learning activities learn more, retain it longer, and like it more than disengaged students. Additionally, this also agrees with the findings stating that through the gamification approach, the students' enthusiasm grew, as did their desire to succeed. The researchers involved Quizziz in their study which addresses a gap in the aforementioned research.

Conclusively, the findings emphasize that better academic performance and engagement are a result of the usefulness of digital learning tools. Review sessions demonstrated that promoting personal involvement improves academic performance. Partaking students in a gamified learning management system may enhance their performance. These studies continuously improve students' motivation and attitudes toward studying by showing a noteworthy association between engagement and academic outcomes through gamified learning. Review games, as opposed to typical teacher-led review approaches, resulted in a noticeable improvement in quiz averages and increased student engagement. In closing, Digital tools as any applications, software, and

platforms that facilitate learner engagement, communication, and cooperation in the construction of curriculum.

Overall, the research provides valuable insights into the perception, effectiveness, and impact of digital tools in online learning for University of Baguio Science High School students.

5.2 Recommendations

This study revealed that students at the University of Baguio Science High School have a generally favorable perception and efficacy of digital tools in online learning. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

1. The students' disagreement or neutrality on particular issues also indicates the need for individualized adaptations to better suit individual learning styles and needs. Teachers are encouraged to explore which digital tools or technologies will be most effective for their approach to teaching and students' styles of learning. This will help students establish a relational knowledge of the lessons.
2. Students are encouraged to make use of or explore digital tools such as Kahoot, Quizizz, and Padlet to further comprehend the materials, regardless of whether the teacher is present.
3. The students are encouraged to be transparent about the use of digital tools during lecture sessions. Given that the online modality necessitates significant exploration of what works most effectively, when teachers adopt digital tools during lectures, students should be outspoken about the efficacy and impact of these digital tools on their learning.

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